

Changing Music Patterns with Change of Geographical Locations with Special impact on GUITAR

Ritu Paban Kotoky, M. Phil. Scholar, Department of Instrumental Music, Rabindra Bharati University,

Page | 303

ABSTRACT

The relationship between music and geography is based on reciprocity. The form and content of music and rendering style witness differences with the change in geographical locations and social structure. The growing complexities in relationships and rapid changes taking place in the socio-political and economic scenario are constantly affecting music, musicians and listeners and consumers of music. These are happening differently in different geographical locations. My presentation will focus on the changed guitar patterns in two geographical locations.

I would like to consider the guitar styles used in Flamenco and Blues those developed in two geographical locations. The music of the guitar that accompanies the Flamenco dance and songs reveals evidence of North-Eastern and Egyptian ancestry. One can feel the structure of rhythmic pattern of Flamenco in Compass Rasguado as 1 2 3 / 1 2 3 / 1 2 / 1 2 / 1 2 / (stress on the last bars). Some popular forms of Flamenco music are Rasguido, Bulerias, Bassanova, Fandango, Rumba etc.

Blues was born in America and became very popular. In Blues they use of Guitar profusely. Here the application of Guitar is clearly different from Flamenco. Popular forms of blues are 12 bar blues and 16 bar Blues. Some genres of Blues are Delta blues, Electric blues, Chicago blues, Country blues, Soul blues, Rock n Roll, etc.

My presentation will go for a musical analysis of these two prominent guitar styles and try to associate influencing factors relating to geographical locations.

Key words: Guitar, Flamenco, Blues, geographical, social

INTRODUCTION:

The relationship between Music and Geography is based on reciprocity. The form and content of Music, its environment, involvement of people, rendering styles all have gone a change with the change in Geographical and Social structure. To reveal this relationship between Music and Geographical location is a subject of research. Geographical investigation of music not only contributes to the growing body of Sociological and Geographical knowledge but is indispensable for better understanding of music in its Geographical and Social milieu. Music is an attempt to make sense of the manner in which we live our life. Geographical location gives us the picture of that society.

In this discussion we will discuss about *The changing music patterns with change of geographical location of a very popular musical instrument GUITAR*. Here we will discuss two most influential guitar styles BLUES and FLAMENCO. We will try to focus on the origin, development, of both the music styles also the particular techniques and elements used in producing its signature form. And most importantly the influence of Geography on that music.

BLUES

A brief Introduction to Blues and its Geographical location:

Mississippi, the birth place of blues is lowland and the poorest state in the United States. People are basically dependent on cotton agriculture. Mainly there were two races in Mississippi- the American whites and the African black people. Its recent population is about 29, 84,926. (United States Census Bureau 2010). Mississippi has a humid subtropical climate with long summers and short, mild winters. It is heavily forested, with over half of the state's area covered by wild trees, including mostly pine, as well as cottonwood, elm, hickory, oak etc. Due to seasonal flooding the Mississippi river created a fertile floodplain in the Mississippi delta.

Mississippi has been known for its music and literature. Musicians of the states Delta region were historically significant to the development of the Blues. Some notable Artist of the region is: B.B. King, Elvis Presley, Britney Spears, and Muddy Waters etc. ¹

FORM and THEME

The blues songs are often sung following a pattern closer to a rhythmic talk than to a melody. The black singer voiced his or her personal woes in a world of harsh reality; a lost love, the cruelty of police officers, oppression at the hands of white folk, hard times. This MELANCHOLY has led to the suggestion of an Igbo (the language spoken by Igbo people of W. Africa, especially in S E Nigeria) origin for blues because of the reputation the Igbo had throughout plantations in the Americas for their melancholic music and outlook to life when they were enslaved. The lyrics often relate troubles experienced within African American society also. Although some songs bear double meaning of with someone coupled with a more salacious physical familiarity. Explicit contents led to blues sometimes being called dirty blues. Lyrical content of music became slightly simpler in post war-blues which focused almost exclusively on relationship woes or sexual worries. Many lyrical themes that frequently appeared in pre-war blues such as economic depression, farming, devils, gambling, magic, floods and dry periods were less common in post-war blues. ²

¹ Wikipedia, the free encyclopaedia, *Mississippi*,

² Wikipedia, the free encyclopaedia, *Mississippi*,

[B.B. King in a performance]

TUNING:

Blues guitar is normally tuned in standard tuning at A = 440

1st string is high E

2nd string is B

3rd string is G

4th string is D

5th string is A

6th string is lower E

(But many guitarist prefer alternate tuning also)

Accompanying instruments

Now days, in blues music, Guitar is the main accompanying instrument, the guitarist have the liberty to play solo parts also, it supports the singer both rhythmically and melodically. Other instruments used in blues are Harmonica, Saxophone, Trumpet, Bass guitar, Trombone and Piano now a days the synthesizer.

The main percussive instrument used in blues is the Drums.

[Pic. : Eric Clapton in Cross road guitar festival]

MELODY & SCALE

In melody, blues is distinguished by the use of the flattened third, fifth and seventh of the associated major scale. These specialized notes are called the BLUE or BENT notes. These scale tones may replace the natural scale tones, or they may be added to the scale, as in the case of the minor blues scale, in which the flattened third replaces the natural third, the flattened seventh replaces the natural seventh and the flattened fifth is added between the natural.

For example,

Normal A major scale is -

A	B	C#	D	E	F#	G#	A
Sa	Re	Ga	Ma	Pa	Dha	Ni	Sa

the A blues scale is -

A, C, D, Eb, E, G, A .
 (SA, komal GA, MA, tivra MA, PA , komal NI , SA)³

RHYTHM

The blues form is a cyclic musical form in which a repeating progression of chords mirrors the call and response scheme commonly found in African and African-American music. There are mainly two types of blues chord progressions. They are: 12 bar blues and 16 bar blues. The basic 12-bar lyric framework of a blues composition is reflected by a standard harmonic progression of 12 bars in a 4/4

³ In Indian classical notation , Sa is the Tonic note , followed by Re , Ga , Ma , Pa , Dha, Ni .
 Komal ga = flattened 3rd , tivra ma = sharp 4th , komal ni = flattened 7th .

time signature.⁴

THE BLUES GUITAR

Normally blues can be played in any kind of guitar. Acoustic blues, electric blues etc.

MUSICAL PATTERN AND ORNAMENTS USED IN BLUES GUITAR

PLAYING

PROGRESSION:

The most popular forms of the blues is the 12 bar blues progression. The term progression refers to a series of chords. 12 bar means the progression is 12 measures long. The three chords used in the basic 12 bar progression are the I, IV, and V chords. For example, the I chord in the key of E is E. The IV chord in the key of E is A. The V chord (dominant) in the key of E is B. The formula for building a 12 bar blues progression is: 4 measures of the I chord, 2 measures of the IV chord, 2 measures of the I chord, 1 measure of the V chord, 1 measure of the IV chord and 2 measures of the I chord. The last measure is sometimes called the TURNAROUND.⁵

$\frac{4}{4}$ | | E - - - | E - - - | E - - - | E - - - | A - - - | A - - - |

| E - - - | E - - - | B - - - | A - - - | E - - - | B - - - | |

STRUMMING PATTERN:-

Usually, blues rhythm is played with a plectrum (a small piece of metal, plastic etc. used for plucking the strings of a guitar or similar instrument). Right hand holds the plectrum to strike the strings. It is held lightly between the thumb and first finger, with one edge striking the strings near the sound hole and bridge of the Guitar. Melodic rhythm is produced by DOWN and UP strokes. Down stroke means the movement of the pick in a downward way. And up stroke means the movement of the pick in an upward motion.

CHORDS

Normal Major, minor, 7th, 9th chord shapes are used in blues music. All open string position, movable barre and half barre chords are used in blues guitar accompaniment.

POWER CHORD

Another popular method of accompanying the blues is to use POWER CHORDS rather than strumming full chords. Only two strings are played on each chord. One of the string may be played open. Here only the Down strokes are used. Power chords may be played on any step of the scale. When playing these chords, only those strings are played which have finger on them. Others should not be touched by the pick.⁶

THE BEND

A bend is played by first picking the string and then bend it upward. Depending on the gauge of the

⁴ Wikipedia, the free encyclopaedia, *blues*

⁵ (Mike Christiansen, *You can teach yourself Blues Guitar*, Page 7)

⁶ (Mike Christiansen, *You can teach yourself Blues Guitar*, Page 12)

string, the guitarist may have to push with more than one finger to do the bend. To get the sound of next half note higher, 1/2 bend and to get the effect of whole note higher full bend is used.⁷

HAMMER ON

A very effective tool in playing blues guitar is the hammer on. A hammer on is performed by picking the first note and without picking the string again, pushing the finger hard on the second (higher) note. The second note should sound clear without picking the string again.⁸

PULL OFF

To play a pull off, guitarist picks the first (higher) note and without picking the string again, pulls the left hand finger off of the string on an angle so the left hand finger actually picks the string and the second note is sounded.⁹

THE SLIDE

Slide is performed by picking the first note and then without picking the string again, slides the same finger on the string to the second note. Two types of slides like slide up and slide down.

THE ARTIFICIAL SLIDE: - Sometimes the guitarists place a slide upon the strings to get a continuous sound. It is made of steel normally.

[pic. the slide]

VIBRATO

One of the most commonly used effects in blues soloing is the use of vibrato. It can be played by rotating on the tip of the left hand finger from side to side (left to right). This is a smooth sounding vibrato. A vibrato may sustain its effect for more than two beats.¹⁰

⁷ (Mike Christiansen, *You can teach yourself Blues Guitar*, Page 31)

⁸ (Mike Christiansen, *You can teach yourself Blues Guitar*, Page 27)

⁹ (Mike Christiansen, *You can teach yourself Blues Guitar*, Page 28)

¹⁰ (Mike Christiansen, *You can teach yourself Blues Guitar*, Page 32)

TURNAROUNDS

A turnaround is a group of notes which are played in the last one or two measures of the blues progression. They signal that the progression is going to be repeated, or in other words it will "turn around". A turn around introduces the first measure. Turn around are very important parts of the blues.¹¹

USING THE CAPO:-

A capo is a clamp which attaches to the Guitar neck and raises the pitch of the notes and chords.¹²

FLAMENCO

"Flamenco is very emotional, yet rigid form of art and an attitude about life. Flamenco means spontaneity and improvisation in music and in life: to live **now** not to give oneself up, to overcome mantel and physical distress without aggression, by using music and dance as an outlet, to accept ones fate, to make the best of every situation, however little that may be and to all this with an enormous zest for life and a strong will to live. This might be the reason why Flamenco is one of the most elemental forms of music making and dancing which exists strongly from listening to oneself".-GRAF MARTINEZ¹³

[Flamenco Guitarist with dancers and other accompanying artist pic. from film Zindagi na Milegi Dobara]

Introduction to Flamenco and its Geographical location:

Before talking about flamenco music let us discuss about its birth place Spain, its Geography and some other things of Spain which can influence its music:

¹¹ (Mike Christiansen, *You can teach yourself Blues Guitar*, page 34)

¹² (Mike Christiansen, *You can teach yourself Blues Guitar*, Page 62)

¹³ (Gerhard Graf-Martinez, *Flamenco Guitar Method Vol 1*, page 6)

Spain is a country in South - Western Europe. A person from Spain is called Spaniard and their language is known as Spanish. Though it is a multilingual, but Spanish is the official language. And culturally, Spain is a Western country. Spain is the world's 52nd largest country. Population in the year 2008 was 46 million people. As recorded by the Padron municipal. Mount Teide has the highest mountain peak of Spain and the 3rd largest volcano in the world from its base . Spain also includes some 15 highly populated Islands. Spain is a mountainous country, dominated by high plateaus and mountain chains. There are also some rivers in Spain. According to Geographical situation and orographic conditions Spain is divided in to three main climatic zones. The Mediterranean climate, characterised by dry and warm summers, the semiarid climate the dry season extends beyond the summer. The oceanic climate winter and summer temperatures are influenced by ocean, and have no seasonal drought.¹⁴

The Arabs ruled in Spain for a sufficiently long period to exercise a sensible influence over the music of the country, and nowhere more strongly than in the province of Andalucía, where the character of Arabian music has been preserved intact. The Spanish popular melodies derived from the Arabs are generally founded upon a series of intervals partaking of the character of the Phrygian and Mixolydian modes of the ancient church music. The church music of Spain however did not appear to have been so much influenced by Arabic music. The Jews had come over to Spain with the Moors (a member of a race of Muslim people living in N W Africa who entered and took control of part of Spain in the 8th century) and the oriental character of their music bore a close affinity to that of the Arabic music. The church music of Spain is based on the Italian model.

There were several kinds of musical drama in Spain. Some were lyrical dramas, some were comic operas etc.

The guitar is the most celebrated of the instruments used in Spain. It is to the accompaniment of this instrument that the young man serenades his mistress, and the labourer, on return home from the day's work, exercises his voice. The Spaniard are singers from nature. They possess an accurate ear. And their songs are characterised by simplicity and feelings, partaking more of intellect and fancy and of romantic and refined sentiment, than of bacchanalian or cosmic expression. The are very fond of introducing embellishments into their melodies , particularly in descending the Diatonic scale, not only in their instrumental performances, but even in their songs. The Bolero, Fandango and Seguidilla, all varieties of the Spanish dance , are executed to the music of Guitar and the rhythmic sounds of the castanets.¹⁵

(Castanets: a musical instrument that consists of two small round pieces of wood that is held in the hand and hit together with the fingers to make a noise . Castanets are used especially by Spanish dancers it's a percussion instrument).

(Bacchanalian: wild and involving large amounts of alcohol)

TUNING:

Flamenco guitar is tuned normally in standard tuning at A = 440

1st string is high E

2nd string is B

¹⁴ (Information from Wikipedia, the free encyclopaedia., *Spain*)

¹⁵ Raja Sir Sourendra Mohun Tagore, *Universal History of Music*, the Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series Office, varanasi, 1963.

3rd string is G
4th string is D
5th string is A
6th string is lower E

Holding the guitar: the flamenco position

[pic: Graf Martinez]

The traditional flamenco way of holding the guitar is to support its weight on the right thigh. This is very different from the 'classical' position, which is not suitable for Flamenco. The larger curve of the guitar is placed on the right thigh, usually on the outer side of the thigh. The right upper arm rests on top of the guitar. The pressure downwards of the weight of the relaxed arm being all that is required to balance the guitar at the correct angle. Neck and shoulder muscles should stay relaxed. Gravity alone maintains the position of the guitar. The right hand forearm is raised by bending the arm at the elbow until the hand, which stays relaxed, lies over the strings of the guitar between sound hole and bridge. The thumb is anchored on the 6th string while playing Rasguado. Flamenco guitar is played with fingers rather than plectrum.¹⁶

Name of the fingers of right hand:

p for pulgar (thumb)

i for *indice* (index or 1st finger)

m for *medio* (middle or 2nd finger)

¹⁶ (Gerhard Graf-Martinez - *Flamenco Guitar Method vol 1*, page 3)

a for *anular* (ring or 3rd finger)

e for *menique* (little or 4th finger)

Left hand fingers are named as 1,2,3,4, -1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th finger.¹⁷

Page | 312

THE CAPO

[pic source : internet, unknown artist]

Its function is to raise the pitch when accompanying a singer. Also, it is used for playing guitar solos giving it a more brilliant tone to the music. It is also known as Mechanical Cejilla. By using the capo we get the open string colour in any fret of the guitar.

[pic:Graf Martinez]

Fingernails of the right hand are very important in playing the flamenco guitar. It is the impact of the

¹⁷ (Gerhard Graf-Martinez - *Flamenco Guitar Method vol 1*, page 12)

nail which makes the string vibrate, so each must be long enough to produce a clean and clear note. The nails must not be so long, that they do not hinder the mobility of the fingers. If the nails are the right length, then in *apoyando* and *tirando* playing the fleshy extremity of the fingertip will just touch the string by the projecting end of the nail. In *rasgueo*, too, the nails are essential in producing the brilliant 'attack' so characteristic of the exciting sound of Flamenco. With the thumb, sound production is by a combination of nail and flesh.¹⁸

THE FLAMENCO GUITAR

[pic source : internet]

¹⁸ (Gerhard Graf-Martinez - *Flamenco Guitar Method vol 1*, page 12)

The sides and back are of light-coloured Spanish cypress this, combined with slightly different wood thicknesses, internal strutting and dimensions, gives the flamenco guitar its characteristic tone, a more penetrating brilliance and vibrancy of response compared to the mellower resonance of the classical guitar. Instead of machine-heads for tightening the strings, the flamenco guitar traditionally has pegs of ebony or, sadly more common now, rosewood or other more easily worked hardwoods. Many flamenco guitars today have machine-heads, but some players still prefer pegs; they are lighter in weight and more durable, and some claim that they impart a more flamenco tone.

The tapa or soundboard of the guitar is made of close-grained German spruce (pinabete) or nowadays often Canadian cedar. The neck is of cedar or hardwood and the fingerboard of ebony. The bridge is palo santo. Nut and bridge-saddle are of bone and in Spanish are called the huesos (bones). The flamenco guitar is fitted with golpeadores or tapping-plates which protect the delicate surface of the tapa from the fingernails and thumb of the right hand. Today these are of transparent plastic. The strings lie closer to the fingerboard both because the bridge is shallower and because the fingerboard is inclined in the portion of overlying the tapa.¹⁹

MODES AND SCALE

Three modes used in Flamenco are – the Ionian mode (the major scale) the Aolean mode (natural minor scale) the Phrygian mode.

Ionian mode : C , D , E , F , G , A , B , C (T,T,ST,T,T,T,ST)

Aolean mode : A , B , C , D , E , F , G , A (T,ST,T,T,ST,T,T)

Phrygian mode : E , F , G , A , B , C , D , E (ST,T,T,T,ST,T,T)

here, T = Tone , ST= Semi Tone

The Phrygian mode has the most characteristic flamenco sound and forms the basis of Gypsy toque. The keys used for the Flamenco guitar are those which include most or all open strings of the guitar (relative to the capo) that is E A G D B.²⁰

¹⁹ (Wikipedia, the free encyclopaedia, *flamenco*)

²⁰ (Flamenco Chuck, *Music Theory For Flamenco*, page 2)

ACCOMPANYING INSTRUMENTS:

[Cajon unknown artist .Pic. source – film Zindagi na mileige dobara]

One of the most important accompanying instrument is the **cajon**, a wooden box drum played with the hands or else it may be played by a percussionist, and all performers will **clap** even if there are dedicated **palmeros**. The so-called Nuevo Flamenco or "new flamenco" may include **flutes** or **saxophones**, a **piano** or other **keyboard**, even the bass **guitar** and the **electric guitar**.²¹

MUSICAL FORM

A typical flamenco recital with voice and guitar accompaniment comprises a series of pieces (not exactly "songs") in different palos. Each song consists of a set of verses (called copla, tercio, or letras), which are punctuated by guitar interludes called falsetas. The guitarist also provides a short introduction which sets the tonality, compás and tempo of the cante.²²

PALOS

Palos (formerly known as cantes) are flamenco styles, classified by criteria such as rhythmic pattern, mode, chord progression, stanzaic form and geographic origin. There are over 50 different palos although some are rarely performed; only about a dozen of these palos are commonly played. Some are sung unaccompanied while others usually have guitar or other accompaniment. Some forms are danced while others are not. Some are reserved for men and others for women while some may be performed by either, though these traditional distinctions are breaking down.²³

RHYTHM (COMPAS)

Compás is the Spanish word for metre and time signature in classical music theory. It also refers to

²¹ (Wikipedia, the free encyclopaedia, *flamenco*)

²² (Wikipedia, the free encyclopaedia, *flamenco*)

²³ (Wikipedia, the free encyclopaedia, *flamenco*)

the rhythmic cycle, or layout, of a palo. The compás is fundamental to flamenco. Without it, there is no flamenco. Compás is most often translated as rhythm but it demands far more precise interpretation than other Western styles of music. If there is no guitarist available, the compás is rendered through hand clapping (palmas) or by hitting a table with the knuckles. The guitarist uses techniques like strumming (rasgueado) or tapping the soundboard. Changes of chords emphasize the most important downbeats.

Page | 316

Flamenco uses three basic counts or measures: Binary, Ternary and a form of a twelve-beat cycle that is unique to flamenco. There are also free-form styles including, among others, the tonás, saetas, malagueñas, tarantos, and some

types of fandangos (Spanish dance).

Rhythms in 2/4 or 4/4. These metres are used in forms like tangos, tientos, gypsy rumba, zambra and tanguillos.

Rhythms in 3/4. These are typical of fandangos and sevillanas, suggesting their origin as non-Gypsy styles, since the 3/4 and 4/4 measures are not common in ethnic Gypsy music.

12-beat rhythms usually rendered in amalgams of 6/8 + 3/4 and sometimes 12/8. The 12-beat cycle is the most common in flamenco, differentiated by the accentuation of the beats in different palos.²⁴

DANCE (Baile)

[Flamenco dance, unknown artist . Pic. Source internet]

Baile flamenco is known for its emotional intensity, proud carriage, expressive use of the arms and rhythmic stamping of the feet. As with any dance form, many different styles of flamenco have

²⁴ (Wikipedia, the free encyclopaedia, *flamenco*)

developed. In the twentieth century, flamenco danced informally at gitano (Gypsy) weddings and celebrations in Spain was considered the most "authentic" form of flamenco.²⁵

MUSICAL ORNAMENTS AND TECHNIQUES USED IN FLAMENCO

GUITAR PLAYING

Page | 317

PULGAR

The Pulgar (thumb) plays an important part in the Flamenco guitar technique. When Flamenco began and the *tocadores* started to play not only chords but also the melodies, they only played with the thumb(p). except for the rasgueos, many guitarists were unable to play with any other finger than with *p*. This led to the invention of techniques which cannot be found in any other kind of guitar music.²⁶

Flamenco Fingernails

pic. : position of thumb in playing Pulgar,

TAP

The tap on the sounding board, or top is very important to play some Flamenco music, because the accent produced by the tap gives a spirit and natural strength for its interpretation without which it would result weak and lifeless. A single stroke (GOLPE) is executed by striking the tapping plate of the guitar with the tip of the middle (m) and ring (a) fingers. The stroke on the strings and on the guitar top are performed at the same time.²⁷

GOLPE

The golpe (beat) is a percussive aid to put more emphasis on the accents or to make the rhythm more interesting. Any beat on the tapa with a finger or the palm is called golpe. A golpe can be

²⁵ (Wikipedia, the free encyclopaedia, *flamenco*)

²⁶ (Gerhard Graf-Martinez - *Flamenco Guitar Method vol 1*, page26)

²⁷ (Gerhard Graf-Martinez - *Flamenco Guitar Method vol 1*, page35)

performed with the ring finger , the middle finger , the thumb or the palm. The golpe with a is most commonly used.²⁸

TREMOLO

Tremolo is a technique for the solo guitar which gives the illusion of two instruments playing together. One, the treble voice, carries a flowing melodic line in which the impression of sustained sounds is created by very rapidly repeated notes, as on the mandolin. The other, the bass voice, plays a rhythmic accompaniment or counter-melody.

Tremolo demands complete independence of movement of thumb and fingers and good control of each finger separately.

The flamenco Tremolo

The flamenco tremolo has five notes to a beat, with an initial thumbstroke on a bass note followed by four tirando strokes with the fingers on the treble; it is therefore written p i a m i. This has one more stroke than the tremolo for classical guitar which is p a m i, the technique used in Tarrega's famous tremolo study 'Recuerdos del Alhambra'.

RASGUEDO

This is one of the most important part of Flamenco guitar . The down stroke and upstroke with the fingers can be combined in countless ways, and there are two different kinds of Rasgueo: the finger rasgueo and the hand rasgueo. The most important thing about the finger rasguao is building up a short tension in the fingers and then flicking them off immediately. In rasguado , the guitarist hits the strings with the fingers of right hand. A single rasguado is executed by placing, or rather anchoring the thumb on the sixth string and is bent. Then close the other fingers and slide them one after another.²⁹

ALZAPUA

The name alzapua (from *alzar* = 'lift' or 'raise' and *pua* = 'point' or 'plectrum') comes from the use of upstrokes with the thumb in this very flamenco technique, which imparts a strongly rhythmic and syncopated pulsation to melodic passages.

TRESILLOS

All 3 finger rasgueos are called tresillos (triplets) in Flamenco, erroneously including rasgueos which are not notated as triplets. No rasgueo is played in so many different ways as the tresillos.³⁰

LEGATO or HAMMER ON and PULL OFF

These techniques are the way of sounding notes using only the left hand. Hammering on, which produces a higher note than the note first sounded by the right hand. Pulling off produces a lower note. A left hand finger stopping the string plucks it by pulling firmly in a direction across it towards the palm and downwards towards the fingerboard.

PALMAS

²⁸ (Gerhard Graf-Martinez - *Flamenco Guitar Method vol 1*,page38)

²⁹ (Mariano Cordoba, *Traditional Flamenco Guitar vol III*. Page 25)

³⁰ (Gerhard Graf-Martinez - *Flamenco Guitar Method vol 1*,page 57)

Etc.³³

ELEMENTS OF FLAMENCO GUITAR:

SOLEARES

Soleares means solitude or loneliness. It is known as the oldest form of Flamenco music and so considered the Mother of Flamenco. This music has a sad sound which expresses the anguish and suffering of the Spanish people throughout the centuries.

The compas of Soleares -

The time value of the Soleares in conventional music is 3 / 4. The rhythm of Soleares is based on a repeated pattern of 12 equally spaced beats, with accents on the 3rd, 6th, 8th and 10th beats and with a more variable accent also on the 12th. Each sequence of 12 beats makes up one compas.

> > > > >

1 - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 - 10 - 11 - 12

AIRE

Aire (literally 'air' and hence 'atmosphere' or 'demeanour') . It means the qualities of animation and expressiveness of a flamenco performance, as determined not only by the form and tempo of the toque but also by the personal idiom and style of the performer. In this way even the same piece of music played by different guitarists can communicate very different kinds of aire. In its most general sense aire is that special magic which gives Flamenco its essential 'Flamenco-ness'. Strict adherence to the compas is a vital part of it, but there is more besides, a quality of meaning which makes the music say something to move the emotions or, at its most intense, to send a shiver down the spine.

The gypsy (gitano) aire tends to be dissonantly oriental in sound, full of irony and passion and perhaps cortado ('cut') by abrupt starts and stops and sudden impulsive accelerations within the overall steady beat of the compas.

At its most personal and idiomatic, aire is that characteristic essence which makes the playing of each of the great masters of Flamenco instantly recognisable and unique.

RUMBA FLAMENCA

Its a popular rhythm among the workers on the sugar and banana plantation of Cuba. The Rumba was adopted to the Flamenco styles, today more popular than original. Traditionally rumba, consists of three chords. but modern flamenco guitarists are no longer satisfied with three note chords. Many rumbas are based on major /or minor tonalities. Rumba is usually notated in 2/4 time. It uses golpe .³⁴

³³ (Wikipedia, the free encyclopaedia, *flamenco*)

³⁴ (Mariano Cordoba, *Traditional Flamenco Guitar vol III*. Page 144)

loud. The thumb plays a melody line in the bass.³⁵

SEVILLANAS

Sevillanas are a lively and tuneful form of Andaluz folk-music. A great variety of Sevillanas, to be sung, danced to and played on the guitar, have become popular throughout Andalucia, and new melodies and verses are continually being created. The strongly rhythmic compas is common to all. The spirit or aire of Sevillanas is usually exuberant and full of alegria and poetic gratia, but some of the melodies and verses are in more serious vein. Those in the Phrygian mode have a typically flamenco character but most often the melodies are in major or minor keys so that they sound more akin to other kinds of Spanish folk-music. The best time to hear the most joyful Sevillanas sung and danced in all their rich variety is at Sevilla's annual Feria or Spring Fair, when crowds in traditional costume throng the streets and gather round the casetas.³⁶

BULERIAS

Bulerias meaning Joy or Happiness, was developed by the gypsies in jerez. The rapid impetus and bouncing pulse of the Bulerias make this the most exciting *toque* In Flamenco. It can be the greatest challenge to the guitarist and the most brilliant showpiece for his virtuosity. It is a *toque* of central importance, with an enormous range and variety of expression possible within it. At its heart is a powerfully rhythmic motor, a driving force which is part of the very essence of Flamenco. The bulerias can be improvised without limitation. The music is believed to be derived from Soleares rhythm.³⁷

The compas of Bulerias

The basic compas of Bulerias follows the same pattern as a Soleares. It is made up of sequences of 12 beats with accents on beats 3, 6, 8, 10 and 12. i.e.:

		>			>			>			>			>
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12			

FARRUCA

People who hail from the provinces of Asturias and Galicia in northern Spain have been called *farrucos*. The flamenco Farruca probably arose in Cadiz by the adaptation of melodies brought there by travellers from these northern regions. Although a *cante* is still sometimes performed, the Farruca today exists almost entirely as a dance-form and as music for the guitar. It is not one of the most profound *toques* but it can make an attractive guitar solo. The chords are played on the guitar in the key positions of A minor, or occasionally other minor keys (e.g. D minor). There may also be brief passages in the Phrygian mode

³⁵ (Wikipedia, the free encyclopaedia, *flamenco*)

³⁶ (Mariano Cordoba, *Traditional Flamenco Guitar vol III*. Page 122)

³⁷ (Mariano Cordoba, *Traditional Flamenco Guitar vol III*. Page 146)

TIENTOS (Tangos)

Tangos are a basic form of flamenco rhythm in 4/4 (or 2/4) time, probably originating from Cadiz and Sevilla . The word tiento literally means a 'touch'. The flamenco Tangos have nothing in common with the Latin-American tango apart from the name. The most lightweight and least intense of the flamenco family of Tangos are the Tanguillos, which are tuneful folk-songs and dances in 6/8 time, particularly associated with Cadiz. The many kinds of Tangos may be known by a rather confusing variety of names such as tangos flamencos, tangos gitanos and tangos (or tientos) canasteros. The music of Tientos is played on the guitar in the Phrygian mode . In addition to the familiar flamenco progression of chords D minor or F, C(7), B , A, there are some falsetas where the chords follow coplas of the cante. Often a singer will end his performance of Tientos with a faster Tangos.

The basic compas of tangos :

4 | > | > | > | > |
 4 1 | 2 3 4 1 | 2 3 4 1 |

CONCLUSION and CONTRAST:

If we look in to geographical account of Mississippi, we get that it is a lowland and the poorest state in the United States. People basically dependent on cotton agriculture. Mainly there were two races in Mississippi . The American whites and the African black people. There was conflicts between the races. The whites dominated the blacks. The blacks were mostly used as slaves. Blacks were not given proper food, cloths, shelter and education was far from them .The behaviour that they got from the American whites, make the blacks very flustered all the time . And gradually their frustration expressed out in their work songs. The colour of their wounded skins became blue. Also their music known as Blues music. These people were not Christian origin. They were converted to Christianity. At that time songs (gospels) were mostly accompanied by trumpets, saxophones and flute. Guitar was not included at that time. It is a later addition . Here a question arises that why blues had grown here ? My own point of view here is that Mississippi entirely composed of lowlands. If we look at the people living near river and mountains, who are poor or middle class and struggles very hard every day to earn bread, generally do not like very complicated music. The do not go to the complexity of musical grammar . Pentatonic scales are in general very simple. I think this is how the minor pentatonic became close to their heart . And this chromatically blue note has a very strong characteristic to express their flustered minds or the melancholy feel. The language of these converted people had naturally happened to be English, as it was colonialism of the Americans .

After years of gradual development, Blues got the structure of what we see it today. Blues is one of the most popular musical genera in world music scenario. The world is thankful to the fertile soil of Mississippi, where blues born and developed. Geographical location is the most influence factor on this music to sound like what it sounds. Its melodies, rhythms, musical patterns all reflect their Geographical characteristics.

CONCLUSION

Finally I found that changes in musicological pattern are directly related with changes in Geographical location. I would like to mention some points here which are responsible for these changes. Like:

LANGUAGE: language is A very important element in any culture. Because people express their

feelings in their mother tongue which is the easiest way of expression. Naturally in case of music also they use to take help of their own language. Music is very much influenced by their language as it creates the form and content of the songs and becomes an inseparable part of such culture.

Availability of material: material influences the culture a lot. Basically people starts to experiment with whatever they get nearby. Like lot of people in Assam plays the Bamboo flute. Bamboo tree is found in bulk in Assam. So it is natural for any Assamese people to experiment with bamboo flutes because of the availability. But people from Bihar or Rajasthan normally don't play this instrument. Because, bamboo tree is very hard to find in those dry places. In the same way in Spain all the materials required to make a guitar is easily available, so most of the Spanish people can play guitar and they play very well.

Religion: music is very close to religion also. Because, our ancient music evolved from religious songs. People belonging to different religion normally do not practice the same kind of songs.

Weather: weather is an important factor influencing the changes. We can say that a sunny weather always leads to happy mood. Cloudy weather makes the mind very dark, but for people belonging to dry area , normally sunny weather get no significance, but those people becomes very happy when ever a drop of rain falls on their head . Eventually their music also influenced by these kinds of changes in weather.

Problems in the society: when some problem is disturbing the people in the society, people normally becomes aggressive. Their rebellious is expressed in the medium of music to reach the society; in that case their music also becomes aggressive, like the blues and rock.

Politics: political atmosphere always influence the socio economic side of people. Musicians are also a part of every society. Musician from a politically stable country generally is happier than unstable political country. And he gets the chance to focus on other parts of life and so his music also flourishes.

Attitude of people: another factor influencing the changes, attitude of the people towards life, history, religion, and of course music makes the changes.

Technicalities of music: Most people don't want to get involve in the technicalities of the music, like grammar, history, theory, structure etc. The country have more technical people produces more technical music. Like blues is mostly played in electric guitar now a days and in flamenco, importance is given on the playing techniques like rasgado , golpe , harmony etc .

Music from Brain and music from Soul: a very small example will clear this fact, like a boy born in a musical family, don't require focusing on the technicality of music very much. He can play most of the music by heart, but a boy belonging to a non musical family has to learn music, after knowing all the technicalities involved there, he can start to focus on the playing.

Day to day work: a day to day wage labour, poor a farmer, a beggar certainly have nothing to do with the technicality of music. They don't even want get involve in those things, but a sophisticated person, doctor or engineer can think and analysis what ever music they listen to.

Physical health: it influences the size of instrument, like American guitars are a bit larger than the guitars manufactured in India; this is for the size of fingers and body of musicians.

Finally we can say that

BLUES IS EXPRESSION OF SADNESS AND FLAMENCO IS CELEBRATION OF THAT SADNESS

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